

Exploring the Transformative Potential of Evocative Interactions with Diffusion Models

Verena Repar
University of Applied Arts
Vienna, Austria
verena.repar@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

echoes of grief is a filmic reappraisal of a fatal loss, delving into the complex interplay between grief, human creativity, and the utilization of generative artificial intelligence in artistic expression. Drawing upon the author's personal experiences and observations, the film is the result of a partly co-creative investigation with a non-human creative instance, while uncovering parallels between co-creation and the process of bereavement. Through qualitative analysis and reflective inquiry, the film uncovers the nuances of acceptance, relinquishing of control, and the emergence of new aesthetic possibilities inherent in this unconventional creative practice. The findings shed light on the transformative potential of integrating generative AI into artistic endeavors, offering insights into the dynamics of human-machine collaboration and the renegotiation of artistic agency within a context marked by unpredictability, serendipity, and chance.

KEYWORDS

Experimental animation, Prompt engineering, Diffusion models, img2img synthesis

Reference Format:

Verena Repar. 2024. Exploring the Transformative Potential of Evocative Interactions with Diffusion Models. In *Extended Abstracts of the Expanded Animation Conference on Animation and Interactive Art (Expanded '24)*, September 5-7, Linz, Austria. 5 pages.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12691593>

1 INTRODUCTION

Diffusion models represent a sophisticated class of machine learning algorithms characterized by their distinctive ability to produce high-fidelity data through a progressive noise augmentation process followed by subsequent noise removal. This methodology facilitates the generation of intricately detailed outputs. At the heart of their operation lies the principle of iteratively deteriorating data integrity, with subsequent restoration to its initial state or transformation into novel representations. Such an approach significantly amplifies the veracity of generated data, thereby unlocking unprecedented opportunities in different domains, particularly in the arts.

The project utilizes the latent text-to-image diffusion model Stable Diffusion [1], a convolutional neural network, trained on 512x512 images from a subset of the LAION-5B database [2]. The code was executed using Automatic 1111 Stable Diffusion WebUI [3], a browser interface using Gradio library [4], featuring intuitive widgets and customizable UI elements. For the creation of the film *echoes of grief* the open-source extension Deforum Stable Diffusion [5] has been used for img2img synthesis of independently created imagery by the artist.

2 SHORT FILM *ECHOES OF GRIEF*

2.1 IMG2IMG SYNTHESIS

In the course of the creative process, the author initially conceived and developed the scenes, landscapes and sets within the digital environment utilizing the game engine Unreal Engine 5 and the 3D modeling software Blender (Figures 1 and 2). Assets were meticulously crafted within Blender and Unreal Engine 5. Within this environment, attention was devoted to the construction of virtual landscapes and the orchestration of camera movements to imbue the scenes with narrative depth and emotional resonance. Subsequently, PNG sequences were extracted and systematically fed into the Stable Diffusion environment, where they have then been processed via [6] image-to-image synthesis, employing a protocol of "Batch Processing" (Figure 4 and 5). Herein, the author exercised precise control over the aesthetic transformation of the visual content, delineating parameters for the generator's influence and guiding its stylization through linguistic "prompts" (Figures 6). These stylized sequences were subsequently regenerated into PNG format, culminating in a corpus of visual data ready for integration within the final cinematic composition. This integration process was executed within the post-production environment of Adobe After Effects, where the individual elements were synthesized into the definitive moving image narrative.

Figure 1: Worldbuilding and Animation in Blender

Figure 2: Worldbuilding and Animation in Unreal Engine 5

Figure 3: Workflow img2img synthesis

Figure 4: Stylization of raw image material

Figure 5: Automatic 1111 Web UI Batch Processing

white marble, rose quartz, abstract rockformations, subsurface scattering, surreal dreamworld, detailed structure, dreamstate, extradimensional, muted colors, calm, wide angle, analogue photography, 8K, film, film grain, film still, Kodak Portra 400

Figure 6: Prompts used for stylization

2.2 EVOCATIVE INTERACTIONS

45 seconds of the short film have been purely generated by Stable Diffusion Deform (Figure 7). For this, a very precise articulation of childhood memories has been required, in order to subsequently create accurate prompts. The qualitative inquiry throughout the creative process of the filmmaking showed, that precise formulation of prompts enables deep introspection, enabling artists to unearth latent memories and emotions. The interactive engagement via meticulous formulation of the prompts with a generative machine unexpectedly yielded therapeutic benefits, evoking forgotten memories and fostering a renewed sense of connection with the past. Furthermore, the work highlights the role of evocative interactions in shaping artistic expression, offering new tools and techniques for exploring the depths of human experience.

Figure 7: Still from an animated sequence generated with Deform Stable Diffusion

»0« : »red childs bike lying in the tall grass, analog photography, rule of thirds, vibrant colors, intricate detail, 8k, filmic, film grain, Kodak Portra 400, DOF, moody lighting, screen space reflections, wide angle, sharp detail«.

»60« : »at the poolside, sunny day, umbrellas, tiles surrounding, underwater bubbles, turquoise water, refractions, filmic, film grain, Kodak Portra 400, DOF, moody lighting, screen space reflections, wide angle, sharp detail«.

»180« : »sitting on your shoulders, shore, waves, me and dad back in 1994, filmic, film grain, Kodak Portra 400, DOF, moody lighting, screen space reflections, wide angle, sharp detail«

Figure 8: Excerpt from evocative prompts

2.3 REMEMBERING THROUGH PROMPTS

Memory can be conceptualized as a dynamic construct, continuously shaped and redefined by the passage of time. Analogous to a film that undergoes modifications with each viewing, memory retains a fluid quality where scenes fluctuate and transform, deviating from their original form. The distinctive visual style of Stable Diffusion Deforum animations, characterized by their oscillating and flickering qualities, aptly encapsulates this transient nature of memory. The perpetual evolution, alteration, disappearance, and re-emergence of images within these animations represent the ephemerality of both time and memory.

The challenge of articulating childhood memories, which reside deep in the past, often initiates an introspective process. A surprising phenomenon arises when prompts related to specific memory motifs are input into a generative model, yielding visual interpretations of those prompts. These generated visuals can evoke long-forgotten memories, which might not be retrievable through verbal or written descriptions alone due to the absence of an external visual representation created by the author. Consequently, this interactive process can enhance the recall of obscured memories, underscoring the interplay between visual representation and memory retrieval.

2.3 CO-CREATION, CURATION & REGAINING ARTISTIC SOVEREIGNTY

The artistic interaction with an AI image generator bears an unexpected resemblance to the process of grief in several respects. Parallels can be observed between co-creation and the experience of loss. A certain relinquishment of control and the presence of unpredictability are intrinsic to creative engagement with these new media.

In this process, generative AI was employed as a creative material. Initially, there was difficulty in letting go of control and allowing the diffusion model to guide the process, requiring a period of adjustment to sit back and wait for the generator's output. Over time, new experiential spaces emerged, accompanied by novel aesthetic possibilities facilitated by automation. The decision-making authority was no longer the central force of the creative endeavor, resulting in a shift towards a curatorial role over serendipitous outcomes.

At times, periods of pronounced vulnerability were noticed, coupled with surprise at the extent to which interaction with an artificial system could align with the thematic contents of the film itself. This dynamic evoked reflections on earlier experiences of loss and grief, when recognizing the lack of influence and control over one's own life and its trajectories.

The process evolved into an exploratory journey, characterized by serendipity, unpredictability, unintended results, and unexpected discoveries. It required a period of adaptation to develop a workflow that reinstated a degree of artistic autonomy and sovereignty. The outcome was a form of controlled chaos. Gradually, the narrative was reclaimed, and a sense of authorship emerged again. However, questions arise regarding the ownership of the visuals, given that the generated content results from stochastic calculations based on an average of six billion images from the internet.

3 CONCLUSION

echoes of grief stands as a compelling filmic exploration of the intricate relationship between grief, human creativity, and the innovative application of generative artificial intelligence in artistic practice. By drawing upon personal experiences and incorporating a co-creative process with diffusion models, the film captures the nuances of acceptance, the relinquishment of control, and the emergence of new aesthetic possibilities that define this unconventional creative journey.

The findings highlight the transformative potential of integrating generative AI into artistic endeavors. The film demonstrates how generative diffusion models can evoke deep introspection, facilitate memory retrieval, and foster unexpected therapeutic benefits. By utilizing language as a medium of creation, artists can delve into unexplored avenues of expression, ultimately leading to a richer, more dynamic interplay between human and machine creativity.

In conclusion, *echoes of grief* not only offers insights into the dynamics of human-machine collaboration but also redefines artistic agency within a context marked by unpredictability and serendipity. This film underscores the significant potential of generative AI to enhance and transform artistic practice, opening new pathways for exploring and understanding the human experience through the lens of technology.

Streaming Link:

<https://vimeo.com/843639604> | password: **echofgr-0623**

REFERENCES

- [1] Rombach, R., Blattmann, A., Lorenz, D., Esser, P. and Ommer, B., 2022. High-resolution image synthesis with latent diffusion models. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (pp. 10684-10695). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2112.10752>
- [2] Schuhmann, C., Beaumont, R., Vencu, R., Gordon, C., Wightman, R., Cherti, M., Coombes, T., Katta, A., Mullis, C., Wortsman, M. and Schramowski, P., 2022. Laion-5b: An open large-scale dataset

- for training next generation image-text models. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 35, pp.25278-25294.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2210.08402>
- [3] AUTOMATIC1111. (2022) *Stable Diffusion WebUI*. GitHub.
<https://github.com/AUTOMATIC1111/stable-diffusion-webui>
- [4] Abid, A., Abdalla, A., Abid, A., Khan, D., Alfozan, A. and Zou, J., 2019. Gradio: Hassle-free sharing and testing of ml models in the wild. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1906.02569*.
DOI: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1906.02569>
- [5] *Deform*. Deform for Stable Diffusion. (2023)
<https://github.com/deform-art/deform-stable-diffusion>
- [6] Meng, C., He, Y., Song, Y., Song, J., Wu, J., Zhu, J.Y. and Ermon, S., 2021. Sdedit: Guided image synthesis and editing with stochastic differential equations. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2108.01073*.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2018.01073>